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² PU: Public, PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services), RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services), CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Deliverable D6.9

The FarFish Database (FFDB)

01/10/2020

Executive Summary

One of many products of the FarFish project is the FarFish Data Base (FFDB), which is intended to make the data collected within the various tasks within the project available for project partners in an operational way. The FFDB is a repository for wide range of data, which allows users to easily upload new data and make queries e.g. for input to visualisation- and decision support tools developed in other tasks in the project. The FFDB is at present available for project partners but will be open access on the FarFish webpage soon and towards the end of the project the relevant datasets will be uploaded from FFDB to OpenAIRE; the data repository of the H2020 Open Research Data Pilot.

A data input protocol for the FFDB (D6.1) was developed within the first four months of the FarFish project. The work on the development of the FFDB has continued since then and the core infrastructure for data collection and on-line visualisation tools was available by the end of the first year of the project (D6.2). This document describes the progress that has been made since then and the current state of the suite of tools developed (FFDB Upload, FarFish DLMtool, FarFish DLMgui, FarFish SPiCtgui and FarFish Maps) in turn, as well as any ancillary work.

The report does as well include a discussion on the work ahead in developing the FFDB further and utilising it in different tasks for the reminder of the FarFish project.

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1 Introduction

The FarFish DataBase (FFDB) is a collection of web-accessible tools to assist with FarFish data storage and visualisation needs. At this point there is a stable FFDB core which provides data storage and a set of web-based interfaces to provide solutions to various problems. In this report we discuss each component in turn, it's role and any work since the previous deliverable, D6.5. For more background on each tool, see D6.5.

All of the tools developed as part of FFDB are part of the FarFish website and can be accessed from <https://ffdb.farfish.eu>.

2 FFDB Upload

FFDB Upload is a structured data input tool that allows FarFish partners to enter and update data sets on case study areas. All data sets are stored on the server and accessible by other partners.

Figure 1: The FFDB Upload interface

Instead of being a single-purpose form, FFDB Upload requests data according to a template, more can be added to allow collection of any kind of tabular data. Data can be exported and imported to/from spreadsheets, allowing more complex editing if required. Data sets are saved onto the FFDB server and can be viewed and edited by other FarFish members. Previous revisions are stored in case of a mistake.

This system has been presented in deliverable D6.2 and D6.5, and a tutorial is available on the FarFish website. Since D6.5, the following additions have been made:

- Any number of abundance indices can be provided, in separate tables with their own scales. This is to support SPiCt, see the FarFish DLMtool section.
- Any errors from performing model runs are reported in the uploader tool.

FFDB Upload is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/upload>, the source code is available on the FarFish GitHub page at <https://github.com/farfish/ffdb/>.

3 FarFish DLMtool

FarFish DLMtool uses FFDB tools to create a data collection tool and graphical front end to the Data-Limited Methods Toolkit [DLMtool]. This is an open-source modelling package designed to evaluate management strategies in data-poor situations. Data is gathered according to the DLMtool FFDB upload template, and then the R Shiny application interfaces to the database to present plots of data and results of DLMtool analysis, demonstrating the outcome of management procedures.

The entire system is web-based, so does not require any knowledge of the R programming language or installing anything on your computer.

Figure 2: The FarFish DLMtool interface

This system has been presented in deliverable D6.5, and a tutorial is available in Deliverable 6.8 (also stored in the FarFish website). Since D6.5, the tool has had major improvements:

The site now supports both DLMtool [DLMtool] and SPiCt [SPiCt] tools, adapting the data provided to FFDB Upload into the data structures required by the models automatically. As well as the tabs available before, you can now also view SPiCt result and diagnostic plots.

To enable scalable support for SPiCt, which takes some time to produce results, FarFish DLMTool has been rearchitected to use a job queue and worker pattern. This is illustrated in the diagram below:

Figure 3: The FFDB worker model

Before, analyses were performed whenever a user requested a graph. Now, multiple workers wait and listen for any new data inserted into the database, and when found run analyses ahead of time. This has multiple advantages:

- We don't repeatedly recalculate the same results when different users request them, they are stored in the database for easy access.
- A large influx of data will not bring down the server (e.g. by using up all memory by performing many SPiCt fits at the same time), since we control how much can be done in parallel by how many workers we run.
- If more capacity is required, more workers can be easily added on other servers. A virtual server could be rented for the week of a workshop to add more workers for example.

There are several dedicated job queueing systems. For example, Redis. However, this requires an extra server component to install. Instead we use the facilities built-in to Postgres. To enable this, support for LISTEN/NOTIFY has been contributed to RPostgres, allowing this software-engineering pattern to be used by any project that requires R workers, thus improving the capability of the R ecosystem as a whole. For more detail on what this is and how to use it, please refer to the vignette available here:

<https://htmlpreview.github.io/?https://github.com/r-dbi/RPostgres/blob/gh-pages/dev/articles/work-queue.html>

As previously mentioned, DLMTool now supports SPiCt. The data added to FFDB Upload is formatted to work with SPiCt and results are seen in the new set of tabs

Figure 4: FFDB SPiCt tabs

In addition, several smaller changes have been made. Colour has been removed from TAC plots. Feedback from workshops showed that the green to red gradient was confused with good to bad. Instead, the TAC plot is now a uniform colour. You can also choose which MPs to display in the TAC plot. More description for each MP method is now offered, as well as a link to further information. There has also been many minor bugfixes and improvements to documentation.

FarFish DLMtool is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/ffdb-dlmtool/> and it's source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/ffdb-dlmtool>.

4 FarFish DLMGui

FarFish DLMGui is an "FFDB-less" equivalent to FarFish DLMtool; the DLMtool template is integrated into the R shiny app, no data is stored on the server, so as a result there are no issues with making DLMGui publicly available. Whilst FarFish DLMTool will be most useful within FarFish due to the data sharing facilities, long term FarFish DLMGui has the potential to increase the impact of FarFish.

The screenshot shows the FFDB DLMtool GUI interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: "FFDB DLMtool GUI", "Edit data", "Catch / Abundance Index Plot", "CAA", "CAL", "Parameter Distributions", "Diagnostics", and "TAC Plot". The "Edit data" tab is active.

Under "Load a DLMtool CSV", there is a "Browse..." button with "Cobia.csv" selected, a "Filename to save as" field with "Cobia" entered, and a "Save data to CSV" button. A blue "Upload complete" button is visible below.

The "Data description" section includes a text area for data entry and a table with the following structure:

	Value
Species	Cobia
Location	
Case study	

The "Catch data" section has "Start year: 1950" and "End year: 2011" fields. Below is a table of catch and abundance index data:

	1950	1951	1952	1953	1954	1955	1956	1957	1958	1959	1960	1961	1962
Catch	104.7041	112.2076	111.3035	128.2866	149.8358	137.8407	162.6785	191.1055	174.8697	205.1042	193.6927	211.9442	224.5
Abundance Index	NA	NA											

The "Catch at age" section has "Bins: 12", "Start year: 1985", and "End year: 2011" fields. Below is a table of catch at age data:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

Figure 5: The FFDB DLMGui interface

This is largely the same as presented in D6.5, however there have been many minor bug fixes. In addition, a user-guide has been written as part of D6.8.

DLMGui is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/dlmgui/> and its source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/dlmgui>. The source code will stay available on GitHub after the lifetime of the FarFish website, instructions on GitHub show people how to install this locally or on their own server.

5 FarFish SPiCtgui

In addition to DLMgui, an equivalent SPiCtgui has also been developed. Like DLMgui, this allows anyone to edit and run SPiCt on their data and can be installed by anyone.

Figure 6: The SPiCtgui interface

As part of D6.8, there is a user-guide for how to use the tool.

SPiCtgui is available on the FarFish website at <https://ffdb.farfish.eu/shiny/spictgui/> and its source code available on GitHub at <https://github.com/farfish/spictgui>. The source code will stay available on GitHub after the lifetime of the FarFish website, instructions on GitHub show people how to install this locally or on their own server.

6 Handsondataframe (HODF)

The core of both FFDB Upload and DLMGui is the spreadsheet-like input table. This is generated by handsontable [HOT], which provides the main grid for data entry. However, in our case we need to constrain columns and rows so we can make sense of the data. For example, we may need a fixed set of rows and columns should be a user-defined range of years. For more information, see the description in D6.5

The main recent change is the addition of the “timeseries” dimension. This allows users to enter monthly/quarterly/bi-annual data into a table without having to update a month column themselves. This is now used for Abundance Indices.

HODF has now been released to NPM, a module archive so it can be easily used in other JavaScript projects, and aim to release the R shiny wrapper to CRAN before the project end.

The format of the table is controlled by the template provided in the fields and values arguments. For more information on how to use these, see the hodef documentation at: <https://github.com/shuttlethread/hodef/blob/master/README.md#templates>.

7 Infrastructure

Servers have been kept up-to-date with security patches, and GoAccess has been installed to provide more statistics of who is using the various parts of FFDB.

Figure 7: Example report page

GoAccess reports work by analysing the webserver logs instead of requiring cookies, and give us insight on:

- Number of users for each tool
- Users geographical location
- Peak usage times
- Operating systems and web browsers that users use

8 Conclusions & future work

At this point we consider the suite of FFDB tools to be feature complete, however bugfixes and support will continue to the end of the project.

The tool will be used as part of training courses elsewhere in FarFish and also to facilitate the communication between stakeholders and scientist when talking about data limited methods for stock assessment and suitable management procedures according to data availability.

A vignette explaining how using RPostgres to create R workers will be created, allowing any user to use the job queue design pattern in their work, benefiting the R ecosystem as a whole.

Where possible, code has been contributed to upstream projects such as DLMtool, and all work in FarFish has been open sourced to maximize usefulness outside the project. Any further opportunities to exploit code built as part of FFDB, e.g. releasing to CRAN, will also be explored.

References

[DLMtool]	Carruthers, T.R., and Hordyk, A. 2017. DLMtool: Data-Limited Methods Toolkit. http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/DLMtool/index.html .
[SPiCt]	<i>Pedersen MW, Berg CW (2017). "A stochastic surplus production model in continuous time." _Fish and Fisheries_, *18*(2), 226-243. doi: 10.1111/faf.12174 (URL: https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12174).</i>
[Shiny]	https://shiny.rstudio.com/
[HOT]	https://handsontable.com/